

Program Portfolio of BIH QUEST Center for Responsible Research

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Background

Economic, social, and cultural challenges are increasingly pushing societal demands for the effective translation of scientific knowledge into societal benefits.^{1,2} At the same time, extensive meta-research has exposed substantial and widespread deficits³⁻⁸ in the scientific rigour, transparency, and reproducibility of research studies, hindering innovation and undermining public trust in science. Inspired by concepts such as Responsible Research and Innovation⁹ or Open Science¹⁰, international organisations such as UNESCO, WHO or OECD call for transformational changes to the scientific system. In this respect, emerging policies address all levels of the scientific ecosystem, expecting research funding organisations and scientific publishers to shape the broader research environment in ways that enable this transformation. At the organisational level, leadership is required to translate policy frameworks into institutional goals, while boards and committees need to take responsibility for establishing governance structures and research environments that enable researchers to address societally relevant research questions.^{2,9,10}

In light of these developments, the Berlin Institute of Health (BIH) at Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin was tasked¹¹ with establishing a translational research ecosystem that effectively bridges scientific discovery and practical application at Charité, one of the largest university medical centres in Europe. To fulfil this mandate, BIH established key translational structures, including the BIH Academy, Charité BIH Innovation, and the QUEST Center for Responsible Research.

Research – Practice – Policy Framework

Since its foundation in 2017, [BIH QUEST Center for Responsible Research](#) has developed a comprehensive, impact-oriented, multi-level intervention program comprising several interconnected sub-programs, projects, and activities that are firmly anchored in a Research – Practice – Policy Framework (**Figure 1**), and share the overarching aim to advance and promote scientific rigour and research integrity, thus increasing the reproducibility¹² of biomedical research studies.

Figure 1 Holistic Research – Practice – Policy Framework of BIH QUEST Center for Responsible Research

1) Research Pillar

The *Meta- and Implementation Research Pillar* aims to identify systemic gaps and weaknesses in biomedical research to inform the design of targeted implementation projects, in which BIH QUEST Center collaborates with clinicians and biomedical researchers at BIH, Charité, and beyond to develop: (i) education and training measures, (ii) digital tools and platforms, and (iii) standards and guidelines that promote high-quality, responsible research practices, as well as (iv) instruments for assessing these practices.

One example for advancing the Center's education portfolio is the [FoRR](#) course, developed in response to the limited integration of methodological training in (under)graduate medical education programmes in Germany. As preclinical research often faces translational failures, referring to research findings that appear promising in early studies but do not translate into clinical application, in other meta- and implementation research projects, BIH QUEST Center advanced two largely neglected methodological approaches: a) confirmation of research findings and b) preclinical evidence synthesis. In the [DECIDE](#) project, the Center worked with a large national research consortium to conduct meta-research and promote confirmatory preclinical studies. Further, in the [COReS](#) project, the Center designed digital tools for preclinical evidence synthesis, developed and delivered in-depth training in preclinical systematic reviews, and established a collaborative platform to support evidence-informed decision-making in preclinical research. Expanding its scope, BIH QUEST Center collaborates with the European Commission and the European University Hospital Alliance ([EUHA project](#)) to advance research reporting through the timely and transparent publication of clinical trial results, including the provision of FAIR¹³ research data, and to promote responsible research assessments through developing appropriate indicators for tenure-track and professorial appointments.

2) Practice Pillar

The *Practice Pillar* is designed to drive tangible change within the institutional research environment by shaping how biomedical research is conducted, evaluated, and reported at BIH, Charité, and beyond. While training programmes remain central to knowledge acquisition, the Center's consulting services and digital tools enable clinicians and researchers to embed high-quality, responsible research practices, addressing aspects such as *research ethics, rigorous study design, conduct and analysis, patient and stakeholder involvement, animal welfare, digital research documentation, timely and transparent reporting, including open-access publishing and the sharing of research data, code, and methodology, and research data management* into their day-to-day work. In alignment with these activities, BIH QUEST Center also provides strategic support to institutional governance bodies, including guidance on responsible research assessment metrics and incentive structures that promote evidence-based organisational decision-making.

Engaging clinicians and researchers

In its role of designing, leading, and administering the strategic building block Responsible Research, BIH QUEST Center engages in organisational strategy development and supports institutional leadership in the accountable implementation of the Charité Strategy 2030. Furthermore, by showcasing its portfolio of support services, the Center proactively engages professors and senior leadership at BIH and Charité through its [Pitching QUEST](#) initiative.

Services and support for researchers

In the scope of its [Education & Training Portfolio](#), BIH QUEST Center offers learning opportunities for all academic career levels that range from introductory to advanced courses, seminars or workshops. Further, the Center designs and implements intramural funding programmes, such as the [PSE Grants and Funds](#), which facilitated the active engagement of patients and stakeholders in the research process, and the grassroots fund [SPOKES](#), which supported early- and mid-career researchers in promoting high-quality, responsible research practices in their immediate research environments. Complementing these activities, BIH QUEST Center provides advisory and consulting services that support research teams and consortia in designing and implementing effective structures and workflows that enable high-quality, responsible research practices. One example is the [Wildling Research Consortium](#), which receives comprehensive advisory support from the Center's [Responsible Preclinix](#) service unit to strengthen external validity and, consequently, enhance the translational potential of its preclinical research. Furthermore, BIH QUEST Center provides comprehensive onboarding support for research teams implementing digital tools, including (i) the [Electronic](#)

[Laboratory Notebook Labfolder](#) to support transparent digital research documentation, (ii) the modular quality management system [PREMIER](#), and (iii) the laboratory critical incident reporting system [LabCIRS](#).

Services and support for governance bodies

To strengthen the responsible research assessment, BIH QUEST Center introduced [Performance-based Incentives](#) at BIH and Charité that incorporate ‘Open Data sharing’ as an additional evaluation criterion for allocating intramural research funds. These efforts are complemented by the [QUEST Awards](#), which incentivise researchers to also implement other high-quality, responsible research practices and to report these practices in their publications. In addition, the Center develops the [MERIT APP](#), an open-source application portal that enables sound evaluation practices for tenure-track and professorial appointments, thus further reinforcing responsible research assessments.

3) Policy Pillar

The Center’s *Policy Pillar* seeks to advance science policies that promote high-quality, responsible research practice and responsible research assessment at institutional, national, and international levels. Central to this effort is the exchange with key stakeholders across the research and science system, including funders, publishers, and patient advocacy groups, through national and international committees and working groups.

At the national level, QUEST representatives, amongst other things, contributed to the development of a national biomedical research strategy through the working group ‘Clinical Studies with Vulnerable Patients’ at the Leopoldina, serve on the steering committee of the [German Reproducibility Network](#), or regularly provide advisory expertise to national funding bodies, such as the German Research Foundation or the Stifterverband. Internationally, QUEST representatives serve, for example, on the Scientific Advisory Committee of [ERA-NET NEURON](#) or lead the CoARA [Working Group SAGA](#) to drive the reform of research assessment methods and evaluation processes.

Monitoring and evaluating responsible research practice

As a founding member of the international [ScreenIT](#) consortium, BIH QUEST Center develops software and digital applications for the large-scale screening of research outputs, including the assessment of methodological rigor and reporting quality in scientific manuscripts. These tools underpin the Center’s monitoring instruments, including the [Charité Metrics Dashboard](#), which tracks the progress of Charité publications across several open science practices. In addition, the [FAIR Data Dashboard](#) assesses the extent to which research data objects shared by Charité researchers and the repositories that host these data comply with the FAIR principles. Moreover, the [Dashboard for Clinical Trial Transparency](#) visualises performance data from interventional clinical trials conducted at Charité and other German university medical centres, using key indicators, such as prospective trial registration, reporting of registration numbers, and timely dissemination of results. These tools are complemented by the [Charité COMPASS on Research Quality](#), a modular (self-)assessment instrument that translates core dimensions of research quality, particularly *ethical and methodological rigour, presentation quality, research relevance, open science, patient and stakeholder engagement, and data management*, into concrete research practices, thus (i) supports researchers in evaluating the current state of their research practices, and (ii) assists reviewers in assessing research outputs such as grant applications, theses, and scholarly manuscripts.

However, biomedical researchers and their organisations operate in complex, highly competitive environments, partially shaped by competing or conflicting norms and values. In this context, Fixsen and colleagues¹⁴ emphasise that implementation in a setting of organisational change is a nonlinear process encompassing six stages: (1) exploration, (2) installation, (3) initial implementation, (4) full implementation, (5) innovation, and (6) sustainability. They further highlight that successful implementation critically depends on leadership, organisational drivers, and dedicated implementation teams¹⁵. To better follow the implementation path to impact, BIH QUEST Center developed the comprehensive **Monitoring and Evaluation System**¹⁶ [COMPASS](#), designed for use across different scales, from individual projects to multi-partner consortia, to systematically track an organisation’s progress, while remaining flexible enough to adapt to the evaluation findings, changing program priorities, resources, or contextual conditions.

Literature

1. United Nations (UN) General Assembly. *Transforming Our World: The 2023 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. 1–35 (2015). <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>
2. Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD). “Addressing Societal Challenges Using Transdisciplinary Research.” Policy Papers, 2020. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/addressing-societal-challenges-using-transdisciplinary-research_0ca0ca45-en.html).
3. Macleod, Malcolm R, Susan Michie, Ian Roberts, Ulrich Dirnagl, Iain Chalmers, John P A Ioannidis, Rustam Al-Shahi Salmana, An-Wen Chank, and Paul Glaszioul. “Biomedical Research: Increasing Value, Reducing Waste.” *The Lancet* 383, no. 9912 (2014): 101–4. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)62329-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62329-6).
4. Al-Shahi Salman, Rustam, Elaine Beller, Jonathan Kagan, Elina Hemminki, Robert S. Phillips, Julian Savulescu, Malcolm R. Macleod, et al. “Reducing Waste from Incomplete or Unusable Reports of Biomedical Research.” *The Lancet* 383, no. 9912 (2014): 176–85. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)62228-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62228-X).
5. Chalmers, Iain, Michael B. Bracken, Ben Djulbegovic, Silvio Garattini, Jonathan Grant, A. Metin Gülmezoglu, David W. Howells, John P.A. Ioannidis, and Sandy Oliver. “How to Increase Value and Reduce Waste When Research Priorities Are Set.” *The Lancet* 383, no. 9912 (2014): 156–65. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)62229-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62229-1)
6. Chan, An Wen, Fujian Song, Andrew Vickers, Tom Jefferson, Kay Dickersin, Peter C. Gøtzsche, Harlan M. Krumholz, Davina Ghersi, and H. Bart Van Der Worp. “Increasing Value and Reducing Waste: Addressing Inaccessible Research.” *The Lancet* 383, no. 9913 (2014): 257–66. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)62296-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62296-5)
7. Al-Shahi Salman, Rustam, Elaine Beller, Jonathan Kagan, Elina Hemminki, Robert S. Phillips, Julian Savulescu, Malcolm Macleod, Janet Wisely, and Iain Chalmers. “Increasing Value and Reducing Waste in Biomedical Research Regulation and Management.” *The Lancet* 383, no. 9912 (2014): 176–85. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)62297-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62297-7)
8. Ioannidis, John P.A., Sander Greenland, Mark A. Hlatky, Muin J. Khoury, Malcolm R. Macleod, David Moher, Kenneth F. Schulz, and Robert Tibshirani. “Increasing Value and Reducing Waste in Research Design, Conduct, and Analysis.” *The Lancet* 383, no. 9912 (2014): 166–75. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)62227-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)62227-8).
9. Owen, Richard, Jack Stilgoe, Phil Macnaghten, Mike Gorman, Erik Fisher, and Dave Guston. “A Framework for Responsible Innovation.” *Responsible Innovation: Managing the Responsible Emergence of Science and Innovation in Society*, 2013, 27–50. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118551424.ch2>.
10. United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). “UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science.” United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2021. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en>.
11. Gesetz- und Verordnungsblatt für Berlin. Gesetz zur Integration des Berliner Instituts für Gesundheitsforschung in die Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin (BIG-Integrationsgesetz) (2020). <https://gesetze.berlin.de/bsbe/document/jlr-BIGIntergrGBErahmen>.
12. National Institute of Health (NIH). “Enhancing Reproducibility through Rigor and Transparency.” Accessed January 12, 2025. <https://grants.nih.gov/policy-and-compliance/policy-topics/reproducibility>.
13. Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.
14. Fixsen, Dean L., Sandra F. Naoom, Karen A. Blase, Robert M. Friedman, and Frances Wallace. “Implementation Research: A Synthesis from the Literature.” *Digest of Papers - IEEE Computer Society International Conference*, 2005, 1–125. <http://nirn.fmhi.usf.edu>.
15. GIZ GmbH. *Cooperation Management for Practitioners - Managing Social Change with Capacity WORKS*. Edited by GIZ GmbH. 1st ed. Wiesbaden: Springer Gabler Wiesbaden, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-07905-5>.
16. Friedrich, Verena, Kathrin Frey, and Lisa Guggenbühl. “Evaluationssysteme in Organisationen.” *LeGes* 32, no. 1 (2021): 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.38023/d10bf5d0-8a27-443c-bb82-33968a5e03ad>.